

Emotional Intelligence and Self-Esteem as Predictors of Psycho-Social Adjustment of First Year Students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Anayochukwu Henry Onoh¹ & Chinenye Virginia Uchenna²

¹Department of Psychological Foundations, Faculty of Education,
Abia State University, Uturu
E-mail: henryonoh6@gmail.com, +2348064142289

²Department of Psychological Foundations, Faculty of Education,
Abia State University, Uturu
E-mail: uchenenyeuchenna@gmail.com, +2348063961945

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Abstract

The study investigated Emotional intelligence and self-esteem as predictors of psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State. Four hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. Correlation Survey Research Design was used in this study. The population used for the study was 320 comprising of all the first-year students of Peaceland college of education, Enugu, comprising of both those studying for Nigerian Certificate in education (NCE) and Degree Certificate. The sample consisted the entire 320 first year students in the Peaceland College of Education, Enugu. Three research instruments were used by the researcher in this study. Students' Emotional Intelligence Rating Scale, Hare Self-esteem Scale and the student adaptation to college questionnaire. Multiple Regression Analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results obtained from the study indicated that emotional intelligence significantly predicted psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State ($P < 0.05$). Self-esteem significantly predicted psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State ($P < 0.05$). Gender significantly influenced the predictive power of emotional intelligence on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education ($P < 0.05$). Also, gender have significant influence on the predictive power of Self-esteem on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education ($P < 0.05$). Based on the findings of this study, some recommendations were noted. The researchers recommended, among others that the college should prepare training programs for students to work on the development of emotional intelligence skills and self-esteem for both gender and for different years and disciplines.

Key words: Emotional intelligence, self-esteem, psycho-social adjustment

Introduction

The transition from secondary school to higher institution exposes students to academic, social and psycho-social challenges. The first year in the college involves a significant life challenge and adaptation to various demands. The higher institutions present students with both new learning experiences and opportunities for psychosocial development (Friedlander, Reid, Shupak & Cribbie, 2007). There is an increase in academic demands and new opportunity to establish social relations (Friedlander, et al., 2007). Life in the higher institutions for the first-year students can be a source of strain and an acute stressor depending on the extent to which the student was able to adjust to different situations in the school.

For some first-year students, entering higher institution may represent the first separation from home, family and friends. There is need to create new relationships, familiarize with new environment, establish a new lifestyle and new routines (Busari & Atinuke, 2019). Difficulty in handling these stressors associated with transition may lead to decreased academic performance and increased psychological distress (Dwyer & Cummings, 2011). The present study will examine how changes in emotional intelligence and self-esteem predict psychosocial adjustment of first year students in Peaceland College of Education, Enugu.

Weiten and Lloyd in Opara and Onyekuru (2013), defined adjustment as the psychological processes by which people cope with the demands and challenges of everyday life. Psychosocial implies association between social factors and the psychological system. According to Madariaga, Arribillaga, and Zulaika, (2014), psychosocial adjustment refers to person's ability to adjust to the environment, which means that the individual has sufficient mechanisms to feel good, integrate, respond appropriately to the demands of the environment and be able to achieve his or her goals. Psychosocial adjustment refers to one's ability to demonstrate positive social skills, psychological functioning and is able to change to meet the demands of the environment (Achenbach, Becher, Dopfner, Heiervang, Roessner, Steinhausen, 2008). Erikson (1963), in his theory of psychosocial development, described the development of healthy personality as gradual mastery of one's environment, which builds towards a unity of personality and a realistic perception of oneself and the world. This growth process involves the individual's physical, cognitive and social development. Studies have shown that positive self-esteem and good emotional intelligence will assist students in coping with the challenges of school and the real world (Fakaruddin & Tharbe, 2017).

According to Mayer, Caruso and Salovey in Fakaruddin & Tharbe, (2017), emotional intelligence refers to the capacity to perceive emotions, assimilate emotion-related feelings, understand the information of those emotions, and manage them. Bar-on and Handley in Ranjha, (2009) defined emotional intelligence as the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions. Emotional intelligence is an individual's ability to perceive, integrate, understand, and manage emotions (Schneider, Lyons, & Khazon, 2013). Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to recognize emotions, to access and use emotions to help support cognitive processes, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to handle or regulate emotions in order to promote emotional and intellectual development (Mayer & Salovey, 2017). An individual with good emotional intelligence is more likely demonstrate a high quality of social and interpersonal relationships, and likely to express love and other emotions. Studies have shown that students who have high emotional intelligence demonstrate better psychological well-being (Palmer, Walls, Burgess, & Stough, 2011) and adjustment to university (Westphal, 2017). Studies have shown that positive emotional intelligence is a predictor of better psychological adjustment and high self-esteem (Bibi, Saqlain & Mussawar, 2016).

Sedikides and Gress (2013) stated that self-esteem refers to individual's perception or subjective appraisal of one's own self-worth, one's feelings of self-respect and self-confidence and the extent to which the individual holds positive or negative views about self. Reasoner (2015) viewed self-esteem as composed of two distinct dimensions: competence and worth. On the basis of these two components, he defines self-esteem as "the experience of being capable of meeting life challenges and being worthy of happiness". Self-esteem is one's feelings, thoughts and evaluations of his abilities in social, education, familial and body image domains (Ghorbanshirodi, 2012).

Studies in the past have shown significant relationship between emotional intelligence, self-esteem and psycho-social adjustment. For instance, Kaur (2015), found a significant difference in adjustment of school students with high self-esteem and low self-esteem. According to the findings, students with high self-esteem have better knowledge of their goals, hence, they never feel stressed as regards to difficult situations within the school. In another findings by Salguero, Palomera and Fernandez-Berrocal (2011) emotional intelligence significantly predicted adolescent psychosocial adjustment. These studies have shown that good emotional intelligence and high self-esteem are imperative for positive psychosocial adjustment among fresh students. Therefore, the present study sought to investigate the emotional intelligence and self-esteem as predictors of psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the emotional intelligence and self-esteem as predictors of psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. Whether emotional intelligence will significantly predict psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State
2. Whether self-esteem will significantly predict psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State
3. Whether gender has any influence on the predictive power of Emotional Intelligence on psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State
4. Whether gender has any influence on the predictive power of self-esteem on psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study, at 0.05 ($P < .05$) level of significance.

1. Emotional intelligence does not significantly predict psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State
2. Self-esteem does not significantly predict psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State
3. Gender does not significantly influence the predictive power of emotional intelligence on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State
4. Gender does not significantly influence the predictive power of Self-esteem on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Methods

Design of the Study

Correlation Survey Research Design was used in this study. It describes the strength of the relation between two or more characteristics (Santruck, 2009).

Population for the Study

The population used for the study was all the first-year students of Peaceland college of education, Enugu, comprising of both those studying for Nigerian Certificate in education (NCE) and Degree Certificate. According to the admission record from Peaceland college, the population of First year students is 320, with 54 males and 266 females.

Sample and Sampling Techniques:

Census sampling was adopted to sample the entire 320 first year students in the Peaceland College of Education, Enugu. The rationale for using the entire population is because it is small and can be managed by the researcher. In other words, there was no sampling of the students.

Instruments for Data Collection

Three research instruments were used by the researcher in this study.

Students' Emotional Intelligence Rating Scale (SEIRS) was used to collect data on the students' emotional skills. The instrument was designed based on Goleman's model of emotional intelligence. It is a 30 items questionnaire measuring five domains of emotional competences, self-awareness, internal motivation, interpersonal skills, mood regulation and empathy (Goleman 1995, 1998). The instrument is divided into five clusters with each of the above domains. The reliability of the instrument was carried out using Crombach Alpha coefficient and it yielded 0.72.

Hare Self-esteem Scale (H.S.E) originally developed in 1985 but revalidated in Nigeria by Anumba in 1995. Hare Self-esteem Scale is a self-esteem report psychometric scale which was developed to measure individual's self-esteem as it relate to peer interaction, homes and schools. The test is one page and contains thirty items. The instrument is on a four-point scales, ranging from strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. This study is adopting the Nigeria version whose reliability coefficient of 0.82.has been determined, there was no need for further reliability estimation.

The student adaptation to college questionnaire. The SACQ by Baker and Siryk, (1989) was used to assess the psychological functioning of the college students. The SACQ contains 67 items with four subscales: academic (24 items), social (20 items), personal-emotional (15 items) and institutional attachment (8 items). Overall adjustment was used in the study by summing students' scores on all the four subscales. Alpha coefficient for the full scale and the subscales ranged from 0.81 to 0.95 among first year university students (Baker & Siryk, 1989).

Method of Data Collection

The researcher used personal – delivery – technique (PDT), that is, the researcher administered the instrument face - face to the students. The respondents filled the questionnaires and immediately returned them on the spot. The total number of 320 questionnaires was administered and all of them collected by the researcher.

Method of Data Analysis

Multiple Regression Analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypotheses One: Emotional intelligence does not significantly predict psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Table 1: Summary of regression analysis on emotional intelligence and psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education

Variable	SS	DF	MS	F	Sig
Regression	5668.72	1	5668.72	1263.74	0.00
Residual	5373.83	318	4.49		
Total	11042.55	319			

The result in Table 1 shows that an F-ratio of 1263.74 with associated exact probability value of 0.00 was obtained. This probability value of 0.00 was compared with significance level of 0.05 and it was found to be significant. The null hypothesis which stated that Emotional intelligence does not significantly predict psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State was therefore rejected and inference drawn was that, emotional intelligence is a significant predictor of psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State.

Hypotheses Two: 2. Self-esteem does not significantly predict psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Table 2: Summary of regression analysis on Self-esteem and psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Variable	SS	DF	MS	F	Sig
Regression	6803.56	1	6803.56	1922.78	0.00
Residual	4238.99	318	3.54		
Total	11042.55	319			

The result in Table 2 revealed that an F-ratio of 1922.78 with associated exact probability value of 0.00 was obtained. This probability value of 0.00 was compared with 0.05 and it was found to be significant because it is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected and inference drawn was that, Self-esteem is a significant predictor of psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Hypotheses Three: Gender does not significantly influence the predictive power of emotional intelligence on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Table 3: Summary of regression analysis on sexual satisfaction as predictor of marital satisfaction among couples

Variable		SS	DF	MS	F	Sig
Male	Regression	1139.47	1	1139.47	161.12	0.00
	Residual	3571.41	53	7.07		
	Total	4710.88	54			
Female	Regression	1463.34	1	1463.34	209.35	0.00
	Residual	4829.90	264	6.99		
	Total	6293.24	265			

The results in Table 3 above showed that an F-ratio of 161.12 with associated exact probability value of 0.00 was obtained for male students. This probability value of 0.00 was compared with 0.05 and it was found to be significant because 0.00 was less than 0.05. The result in Table 3 also showed that an F-ratio of 209.35 with associated exact probability value of 0.00 was obtained for female students. This probability value of 0.00 was compared with 0.05 and it was also found to be significant. The null hypothesis which stated that Gender does not significantly influence the predictive power of emotional intelligence on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State was therefore rejected and inference drawn that, Gender significantly influenced the predictive power of emotional intelligence on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education

Hypotheses four: Gender does not significantly influence the predictive power of Self-esteem on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Table 4: Summary of regression analysis on sexual satisfaction as predictor of marital satisfaction among couples

Variable		SS	DF	MS	F	Sig
Male	Regression	1471.20	1	1471.20	176.62	0.00
	Residual	5097.76	53	8.33		
	Total	6568.96	54			
Female	Regression	1124.41	1	1124.41	204.70	0.00
	Residual	3207.91	264	5.49		
	Total	4332.32	265			

The results in Table 4 revealed that an F-ratio of 176.62 with associated exact probability value of 0.00 was obtained for students in male students. This probability value of 0.00 was compared with 0.05 and it was found to be significant because 0.00 was less than 0.05. The result in Table 4 also showed that an F-ratio of 204.70 with associated exact probability value of 0.00 was obtained for female students. This exact probability value of 0.00 was compared with 0.05 and it was also found to be significant. The null hypothesis which stated that gender does not significantly influence the predictive power of Self-esteem on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State was therefore rejected and inference drawn that, gender have significant influence on the predictive power of Self-esteem on psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education.

Discussion of Findings

The findings showed that emotional intelligence significantly predicted psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State. This finding gained support from works of previous researchers such as Adeyemo (2005) who found that emotional intelligence is significantly related with secondary school students adjustment to school. The finding is also in agreement with Salami (2011) who found that emotional intelligence significantly predicted first year students from colleges of education in Kwara State. A possible explanation for this finding could be that the students possessed the ability to access, understand, express and regulate emotions which resulted in promoting their emotional and intellectual growth. This resulted in their ability to cope adaptively with their academic, social and personal-emotional challenges in their new college environment. However, the present finding is dissimilar with Bang and Sim (2012) who found no significant correlation between emotional intelligence and adjustment to college life in nursing students. Furthermore, emotional intelligence helps one build stronger relationships, succeed at school, and achieve career and personal goals (Moghal, Yasien, Alvi, & Washdev, 2016). Persons with high emotional intelligence tend to have better social skills, are perceived

as more pro-social and less prone to conflict, better physician-patient relationship, better patients' trust and better patient outcomes (Cherry, Fletcher, & O'Sullivan, 2013).

Further findings indicated that Self-esteem significantly predicted psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State. A possible explanation could be that the students believed that they were confident and that they were capable of handling any academic, social or personal-emotional challenges that they faced as new students in their college. This result was similar to Evans, Levy, Sullen-Berger and Vysa (1991) who reported that there was a significant relationship between self-concept and students' adjustment to school. It has been demonstrated that an individual with a high self-esteem has a better level of mental health and self-harmony (Peng, Cheng, Chen, & Hu, 2013), feels more confident and more competent, exhibits optimistic attitudes (Rutter, 1997), has strong personal strength and ability to solve problems and ability to control emotions (Eremie, & Chikweru, 2015).

In addition, it was found that gender has a significant influences on the predictive power of emotional intelligence and self-esteem in determining psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State. This finding supported the earlier studies by Bibi, Saqlain & Musawwar (2016) and Walsh and Joyce (2011). Several studies argued that women tend to be more emotionally intelligent because they received education biased towards emotions while men are taught to minimize certain emotions related to sadness, guilt, vulnerability and fear (Brody & Hall, 1999; Sánchez, Fernández Berrocal, Montañés, & Latorre, 2008). Studies also conclude that women have a greater emotional knowledge and tend to express their emotions more fluently and more frequently and can easily adapt themselves socially compared to men (Brody & Hall, 2000; Ciarrochi, Hynes, & Crittenden, 2005; Hall & Mast, 2008). Acceptance and social support received by female students at the university also affects the high level of emotional intelligence.

Conclusion

The study investigated Emotional intelligence and self-esteem as predictors of psycho-social adjustment of first year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State. Following the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Emotional intelligence significantly predicted psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State.
- Self-esteem significantly predicted psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State.
- Gender has a significant influences on the predictive power of emotional intelligence and self-esteem in determining psycho-social adjustment of first Year students of Peaceland College of Education, Enugu State

Recommendations

Sequel to the findings and discussions from the study; the following recommendations are made:

1. In order to impact positive self-esteem in students, parents, teachers, educational psychologists and counsellors should provide the students adequate orientation towards the development of positive self-esteem.
2. The college management and counsellors should try to inculcate high emotional intelligence in their students to facilitate their quick and smooth adjustment to school.
3. The college should prepare training programs for students to work on the development of emotional intelligence skills for both gender and for different years and disciplines.

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